

Face Recognition for Surveillance Systems using SRGAN

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Abstract- *In this current era, surveillance systems are being installed in all crucial places such as banks, malls, houses and many such places. The main reason for this is security and to achieve this crucial objective, face recognition becomes important. Face recognition is an important factor which becomes one of the factors for growth in technologies such as Computer Vision, Pattern Matching and Artificial Neural Networks. Face recognition has been a major challenge in the field of computer vision since it has to encounter a series of implementations for successful execution of identifying a particular face in the video from a surveillance camera. There are many factors such as light conditions, facial expressions and poor quality of the surveillance device, that affect the implementation of recognizing a face from the image or the video captured by a surveillance system. Hence the images recorded in such conditions require special attention and hence need to be enhanced for better results. The aim of the paper is to provide various methods to provide an efficient facial recognition method with minimal cost and high efficiency.*

Keywords : Face identification/recognition, surveillance system, computer vision, Pattern Matching

1. Introduction

Face recognition is a complex task which is being researched on for decades. Face detection and recognition has been an immense challenge since it has to undergo various considerations before obtaining the result. Some of the applications where face recognition is highly useful are for access control, face identification and further authentication and also face recognition in surveillance systems for security purposes. The surveillance systems are also being used in the military and traffic signals, ATM surveillance, colleges and offices. The main criteria for face recognition involves obtaining maximum data on the face and the structure of various faces that will be captured on camera in order to provide high performance and efficient application that recognises faces from the captured images successfully. There are various algorithms being used in the current generation with different approaches and yet an optimal efficiency is not gained by the users. The methods such as pattern matching, color segmentation, Eigenface determination, Euclidean classifier and fields such as Computer Vision, Artificial Intelligence, Image Processing and many more overlap with each other to provide an

efficient solution to attain the objective. One method would be to recognize a face by using estimation algorithms and by matching a random face image. A facial structure can be recognized by comparing the faces with a set of face images stored within a database. The human faces are unique and hence the characteristics are dynamic in nature. Face coordinates, skin condition, illumination, eye structure etc are considered for face recognition.[1]

One of the important implementations of face recognition is security. Security attributes such as keys, passwords, ID cards etc are traditional methods to gain access control or to authenticate one's identity. However these methods are not optimal due to which biometrics came into existence as an application for security purposes. Biometric is a unique method and helps in identifying each person with a unique characteristic feature of that person but this means the use of a fingerprint scanner or a DNA analyser which increases the expenditure for the availability of the devices. Also in current scenarios it would provide high risk of transmission of virus by using the same device with every individual.[2]

Face recognition is a better and efficient method as it does not provide for such disadvantages and also since a face structure has stable features and also each individual has different facial characteristics and cannot be duplicated.

Face detection must be implemented before a face can be recognized within the image captured through surveillance cameras. Once face detection is successful face recognition can be considered just as image matching.

In today's technological world, Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning are trained for several images contained within a dataset. Pattern Matching can be performed in an instant on many images present in a dataset for the availability of a particular face among all the images within the dataset. The algorithms have some drawback wherein the facial expression of a individual might be varying or the image is captured in a advert lighting condition where the face is not detected efficiently and hence fails to be recognized.[3]

There are various methods such as generative adversarial networks, an algorithm of machine learning to overcome the drawbacks and provide us with clear and high cut resolution, sharp images. There are various methods and implementations that overcome and can detect the face efficiently.

Face recognition is also being used in smartphones where the artificial neural network tries to recognize similar face from different images which is commonly seen on Google Photos and also many of the phones have the feature wherein when a face is being captured it tries to detect the age of the person and many more of such present generation features requires face detection as well as face

recognition.[4] These features can also be used among the images captured by a CCTV camera.

This paper involves a thorough study and notes down the disadvantages and provides an efficient solution that can be implemented for obtaining an optimal result of face detection and consecutively face recognition.

2. Related Works

In this section, a survey analysis of the different proposed methods over the past few years for face detection and face recognition of images and videos tapes obtained through surveillance systems (CCTV) is presented so that by analyzing the drawbacks of such methods we gather information and provide a solution for the drawbacks and hence obtain an optimal and efficient method to detect and recognize a face from a surveillance camera.

Face Recognition in Real-world Surveillance Videos with Deep Learning Method[5]

This paper provides for a robust solution for face recognition that can be used in the application of security systems. Deep learning is used for implementing the goal of face recognition. The model basically is trained using a novel dataset obtained from a target real-world surveillance system. The model is trained to detect, track, label and purify the images. Finally this trained convolutional neural network model is tested on a real time surveillance system which detects the face and tries to recognize the face from the images captured. This model achieves a good result of 92.1% recognition accuracy. Hence the method proposed in this paper uses both supervised and unsupervised learning mechanisms. The dataset creation was manually done and hence the proposed model is expensive since dataset creation and labelling requires a lot of time and workpower but the advantage is that the model is successful to recognize the face of people with different expressions and amid various lighting environments.

Face Recognition in Surveillance System [1]

The paper proposes to use processing 2.1.1 of the open cv library in computer vision. This comes under the machine learning domain. They have also proposed to use matlab and using the two libraries together obtain the feature extraction facility which becomes very important when the model has to detect or recognize an individual's face from an image. Image segmentation, feature extraction and template matching are some of the steps that are included for successful face detection. The feature extraction uses PCA(Principal Component Analysis) and for template matching a part of the captured image face that is already detected successfully is matched for identification and this uses Eigenvalue represented by Eigenvectors. The

approximate success rate of this method is 92% which used 4 training faces and 28 number of Eigenfaces.

Surveillance Camera using Face Recognition for automatic Attendance feeder and Energy conservation in classroom [6]

The paper proposes to use Face Recognition from the video captured by the surveillance systems as an application for Attendance marking purposes as well as conserving the extra power wasted within classrooms on a daily basis. From the group image captured in each class from the smart camera, the frames are divided and sent to the face detection algorithm. Haarcascades classifiers are used to extract the faces from the group image captured by the smart camera since it provides decent accuracy and in this process most of the values are already available. For instance the distance from where the images will be captured is constant everyday and will not be altering and as well as the face pictures of the students can be fed into the model beforehand since they are countable and are limited in number. A deep learning convolutional neural network is used to optimize. The triplet loss function is used to train. This method works efficiently in a school environment but is not robust and does not work if the dataset of images are too large.

Face Detection for Security Surveillance System[7]

This paper provides the solution for face detection by using Haar rectangle as its feature, and selecting appropriate classifiers through the AdaBoost learning algorithm. The image when detected is labelled along with the time it was captured and stored into a database and hence helps in providing information about an individual for security purposes. This paper overcomes the disadvantage of face recognition that couldn't be carried out in certain special circumstances. For one face detection, there will be a large number of rectangle features and hence AdaBoost is used here to select the features and also train the classifier accordingly using these features. The system works only for black and white images captured from CCTV surveillance and does not provide any assurity of the speed with which it can capture and save the details within a database. The paper says that Haar rectangle and AdaBoost is a good method that can be used but if used with deep learning classifiers or Artificial Intelligence has a scope of obtaining better results.

Vision-Face Recognition Attendance Monitoring System for Surveillance using Deep Learning Technology and Computer Vision. [8]

The paper proposes to use Artificial Intelligence to provide the solution of face detection and recognition. A neural network developed using Artificial Intelligence and Machine learning can be trained on billions of images and can be used to detect a face and then learn the face to recognise the

image. The face detection would not work properly for many reasons such as artificial lighting, smart camera limitations or poor quality image processing. Mainly the artificial neural network is used to detect the face and then further train the recognizer model and finally perform the task of facial recognition. Face detection is done using the Haar Cascade Method that identifies the face and objects surrounding it. The identification of face and the non face image is carried out and classified into its respective classes. They have considered features with minimum error rates such as eyes and so on. The paper provides for a detection accuracy of around 70% and is not the optimal solution available in the industry.

3. PROPOSED MODEL

The various surveillance systems used in the current world require a face recognition and further detection system for various applications. Such systems require an enhanced model that accurately performs the function and various tasks and serves the users with a positive experience. The model that is being utilised is the SRGAN model. The super resolution generative adversarial network model enables us to use machine learning in an effective manner to be able to detect and recognise facial structures in different parts of the day efficiently. Hence in this paper we propose a SRGAN machine learning model to perform the given task.

GANs are a class of machine learning systems that work on the basis of two artificial neural networks competing against each other. It consists of a generator network and a discriminator network. Generator network takes in noise usually as input and tries to model it into a required data set, thus creating realistic outputs in the process. The discriminator network is used to judge how realistic the output from the generator network is. Thus the two networks compete in a non zero sum game. The Discriminator is trained using supervised learning in the beginning so that it can classify the inputs from the generator into true or false values. Then the two networks are allowed to train unsupervised providing better and better lifelike results. The paper proposes a model where the generator will be fed with various images and be trained to recognise images and when the discriminator is given an input it automatically can detect the facial structure of the image. The advantage here is that since this model is a machine learning model, numerous images can be used as training dataset for training the network.

The two models are trained using unsupervised learning and hence they learn new facial structures as and when they come across an input image with new data available to learn. The two models work on the basis of zero sum game that is the generator tries to upscale in a way that it wants the discriminator to make a mistake and on the other side the discriminator model tries its best to identify the images and hence recognise and detect the faces efficiently without being fooled by the generator. The two models try to be the best so that the other does not win the game. The GANs are formulated as a minimax game that will compete with each other[10].

The adversarial network can be used for multi purpose and hence it acts as a single architecture. This provides for an advantage that the model would be able to recognize and detect as well as enhance the image quality. Hence this single architecture provides for various image processing tasks and helps us achieve better PSNR values of images we procure from a surveillance camera. The architecture of the proposed model is given at a detail in the subsection.

3.1 Architecture of the Proposed Model

The two networks help us achieve the desired results. The task in hand is to successfully be able to detect a face from an input image and recognition of that face if that face has already been registered by the model else add it to a database. The input image is given to the generator network of the proposed model of size 128x128 pixels as shown in figure-1a and this model takes in consideration all the colours that are red green blue and hence facial recognition becomes easier with the colour type not being suppressed.

Two residual networks are added within the model for up-scaling of the images and these layers perform a 4x scale up of the image quality. The residual networks are layers within the model that are used to connect the input layer to the output layer and perform some minor functions when travelling. A convolution neural network is used for sliding the filters over the image. It is used for filtering, segmenting and classifying the inputs. The filters used as a parameter in Residual Network also are a method to change the image in a certain way to provide a better result.

This model uses various catalyst techniques for the training of the network. Batch normalization is one such method which reduces the number of epochs which are required for stabilizing the entire training period. Finally we obtain the output of the generator using the tanh function. The image obtained as the output is upscaled to size 256x256. The tanh function squashes a real-valued number to the range [-1, 1]. Its output is zero-centered.

We train the SRGAN to learn how to perform the different tasks. We provide the down-sampled images with facial characters and let the generator produce a real-like up-scaled image of the input and train it to detect and store various facial images and the data of such images along with the image detected. The discriminator if identifies the image as fake then the difference of the real image and the image produced by the generator is the noise which is used for the backpropagation and the generator and the discriminator learns from the tasks. The discriminator also if successfully recognizes and detects the faces provides for a positive feedback else goes for back propagation. This task is for the system to learn to produce better resolution images with better destruction and recognition skills. For denoising, we feed images with high noise as inputs and for deraining we send images with the rain droplets on the images as input. Hence for training we need to put loads of images so that the model is able to detect and keep information of several facial pictures of the images.

Figure 1a- Architecture of the generator

The input of the discriminator is 256X256 due to the upscaling of the images that takes place in the generator and this is depicted in figure-1b. The work of the discriminator is to detect the facial structures effectively from the images generated by the generator. The layers of input are provided by the convolutional network and it is used as a linear non-saturating method and finally output layer is added to detect the facial structures efficiently and this is efficiently depicted using the sigmoid function.

The activation of the model is done using the rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) with threshold being at zero value. This function has various advantages such as it greatly accelerates the noise function of the gradient descent and hence helps in providing a clearer image. This occurs due to its linear, non-saturating and many more features of the descent function. This unit is simpler to implement than the output functions such as sigmoid and tanh. Leaky ReLU is more advantageous since ReLU are highly sensitive and hence they have an advantage having a small negative slope to increase the range of the unit.

Every layer is connected to another layer including the input to every output using dense layers. These layers result in the output based on the units present as input to each of these units. These units have approximately 1024 neurons and help in providing information to the next neuron based on all the previous calculations made. Dense keyword, batch

normalization allows us to stabilize the output of the model by making them a standard value such as these values must have a mean of 0 and standard deviation as 1. The leaky ReLU is used as a method activation.

The output for the discriminator uses the sigmoid function. Sigmoid helps any user to identify if the model is accurately able to detect or not by giving output in the form of 0 or 1,0 being for failure and 1 being for being able to successfully detect the face from the image. Therefore, it is especially used for models where we have to predict the probability as an output. Since probability of anything exists only between the range of 0 and 1, sigmoid is the right choice. This is used to calculate the error and is used for the backpropagation training of the generator and in turn also for the training of the discriminator.

Figure 1b- Architecture of the Discriminator[21]
4.IMPLEMENTATION

The domain used is Machine Learning and hence the code is written in Python since it offers various libraries. GAN is a subdomain in Machine Learning. It also uses a combination of the Image Processing since the images have to be processed to get a higher resolution of the input image. Machine Learning has been used in many domains and the implementation of the algorithms in CCTV real world application will help in a lot of aspects such that it becomes a benefit to society. The crime scenes can be recorded with clearer images which would help as vital evidence. It also helps us record each and every detail due to the high resolution.

The execution of a plan or an idea or the entire model and also the working of the entire model is the implementation process, It can also be the execution of the design, specification, standard, algorithm or policy. The training and testing is the main steps of the implementation of this model of the two artificial sub neural networks. The sum of the win and loss must be equal to one. Loss functions are introduced to perform various tasks and to reduce the casualties of the model and also help with the back-propagation. This helps us in achieving better results.

The loss function is aimed at reducing artifacts introduced by GANs and ensures better visual quality. We use two loss functions namely the Adam stochastic Gradient Descent and the Binary Cross Entropy Loss function for achieving the error value and using this value for the backpropagation algorithm and further training the model.

The basic steps used for constructing and predicting the module with the help of keras[21] is:

1. Creating the network architecture with standard keras classes. Examples are Sequential, **Dense**, **Conv2D**, **Upsampling**, **BatchNormalisation**.
2. Compiling the created model using **model.compile()** method.
3. Preprocessing the input dataset into tensors or by converting them into numpy arrays.
4. Preprocessing the target values for the dataset and converting them into tensors.

The first layer of the network or model will take an image with facial and objects of other matter as input and is completely connected as it is just a matrix multiplications of the pixels of the images but the result is reshaped into a 4-dimensional tensor and used as the start of the convolution stack. For the discriminator, the last convolution layer is flattened and then fed into a single sigmoid output.

Batch Normalization becomes very critical when dealing with this model since when deep generators begin the learning process, they prevent the generator from collapsing all samples to a single point which is often a common failure mode observed in GANs. Directly applying batchnorm to all layers however, resulted in sample oscillation and model instability. This was avoided by not applying batchnorm to the generator output layer and the discriminator input layer. We observed that using a bounded activation allowed the model to learn more quickly to saturate and cover the color space of the training distribution. Within the discriminator

we found the leaky rectified activation to work well, especially for higher resolution modeling.

The discriminator takes the x and x' as its input which is the real image and the image generated by the generator sub-network. A discriminative model is the one that can only be used to **discriminate/classify the data points**. You only require to model $P(y|x)$ in such cases, (i.e. probability of class given the feature vector). The real sample and the fake sample are labeled as 1.0 and 0.0 respectively and the probability is determined by the discriminator. This value is used to help the model to calculate the error value. If the value is close to 1.0 the probability is high and might be taken as real and hence is used to train the discriminator to not get fooled again. If the value of probability is low the generator is trained to produce better fake images. All models were trained with mini-batch stochastic gradient descent (SGD) with a mini-batch size of 20. All weights were initialized from a zero-centered Normal distribution with standard deviation 0.02. In the LeakyReLU, the slope of the leak was set to 0.2 in all models. While previous GAN work has used momentum to accelerate training, we used the Adam optimizer with tuned hyperparameters. We found the suggested learning rate of 0.001, to be too high, using 0.0002 instead. Additionally, we found leaving the momentum term β_1 at the suggested value of 0.9 resulted in training oscillation and instability while reducing it to 0.5 helped stabilize training. These are some of the parameters that were found to be working well with stabilized and efficient results.

5.RESULTS

A neural network contains hundreds of thousands of trainable parameters for which the gradient has to be computed in each epoch. The general implementation of a model is done using matrices on a dedicated GPU. The keras module uses a decent CPU or GPU for processing and executing the python converter file. Due to this factor Google's Colaboratory feature was used to train the model.

Google colab that allows you to start working directly on a **free Tesla K80 GPU** using Keras, Tensorflow and PyTorch, and how we can connect it to Google drive for the data hosting. It also gives you a total of 12 GB of ram, and you can use it up to 12 hours in row. Google Colab provides RAM of 12 GB with maximum extension of 25 GB and disk space of 358.27 GB.

Some of the observed results are depicted in figure-2 where the images are captured from an external CCTV camera and the images within the frames have been processed through the proposed model and the resolution has increased and thus provides a better quality image with reduction in the noise and hence better user experiences. The image provides a better vision and helps in many applications in the field of computer vision.

a) Input frame

b) Output Frame

c) Input frame

d) Output Frame

Figure-2 Frames captured using surveillance system (a,c) and the enhanced version of the image along with facial detection in the frame using the proposed model (b,d)

3. Conclusion

The paper discusses the various methods and implementations of face recognition and detection from images or videos that are captured from a surveillance system. Accordingly, the process of face recognition of a surveillance system has three different stages, and each of these stages are important for obtaining the final result in an efficient manner.

Before the stages are implemented the images captured might have lighting effects or can be of poor quality. To overcome such issues we need to preprocess the image such that the frames of the image are clear and hence face erection can be done efficiently using a neural network. The stages are face detection from the images which can be in any format such as it can be a 2D or a 3D image or can be a part of the video captured and hence the frames are divided

and face detection algorithm takes place. The second stage would be to extract features such as any facial landmarks or any marks that would easily help us recognize the image. The features would also include different parts of the face. The final stage would be the face recognition which refers to the matching of the face or the features with the database consisting of already trained and hence recognized faces.

The purpose of this paper was to summarize the different approaches implemented for facial recognition from images and videos and hence proposing the different methods for face detection and recognition. The search for an ideal method that recognizes a face from an image accurately is still an issue in the world of technical research and analysis. The main criteria looked upon is the efficiency of the method and the time required for the operation to be completed. In future courses other criteria such as various resources utilised and the reduction of cost would come into consideration. Each method has its own advantage and dis-

advantage. By combining the advantages of many models we can find a new affordable and adoptable solution which makes an efficient model that provides huge efficiency and has time as a benefit.

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